

The Reciprocal Reading Strategy to Improve Reading Comprehension in Self Directed Learning

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Abstract

Lingo society undergoes versatile changes in the arena of Reading strategies. The present study investigates differences of these strategies, evolves the research avowal "The Reciprocal Reading Strategy to improve Reading comprehension in self-directed learning". The strategy applied to check the improvement was; "RRS", a structured method of guided reading. RRS and CRM were applied to see the differences of strategies; in English subject. It was experimental study. 200 Students from the District Mardan were selected through stratified random sampling technique. G1 was taught with RRS while G2 was taught by using CRM. From pretest it was found that both groups proficiency level are same as the target strategy (RRS) stood stagnant being not applied initially. The posttest analysis depicted t- value 11.498; p- value .000 ;G1 scores remains 6.65662 while G2 4.57909 and mean of score differences 9.29000 were at significant level of 0.05 so the null hypothesis was rejected and alternative was accepted.

Key Words:

Reciprocal,
Strategy,
Conventional Reading,

Introduction

Background of the Study

Generally speaking, of all the language skills, reading has got some imperative role. Carrying such saying of significant value; it is highly regrettable to locate our country sides schools (Pakistan), where such skill has not been developed since longer .By and large in rural areas such proficiency is being ignored to great extent when the students reach to the intermediate level, they remain incapable of producing a good piece of paraphrasing. Many theorists and psychologists worked on this essential part of the skill. Bloom's taxonomy or Vygotsky's comprehension models, Gagne's instructional model or Pearson responsibility model; keep vibrant role in reading comprehension at various levels. In these circumstances to prevail the importance of reading habit, various strategies can be demonstrated.

Alan and Jay (2008) contributed much for the development of Vocabulary Instruction. They consider it as a critical component for skillful Reading. In their Edition *What Research Has to Say about Vocabulary Instruction*, the authors deliberately gave detail studies of theory, Research and instructional guidance for the development Reading and vocabulary construction.

Robert Gagne worked on verbal instruction gives a unique way of language instruction. He verified the innovative way of instructional model for reading comprehension as well as other language skills (Gagne, 1970).

Studying second Language acquisition; the Linguist theorists constructed different approaches in order to make it easier for nonnative speakers being able to learn all the four skills (Listening, Reading, Speaking and Writing) by practicing such approaches in class room environment. They used Audio lingual, Grammar translation, Natural approach and interactive approach for the improvement of Reading and Speaking second Language. Even then the result had not been remained satisfactory especially in Pakistan. (Teaching English, 2012).

Reciprocal teaching is an excellent reading device in the field of self-directed learning which helps to improve reading comprehension and also assists teachers in the teaching practice. "Reciprocal is an instructional activity in the form of a conversation amid teacher and students concerning part of content in which participants take turns assuming the role of a teacher" (Palincsar , 2010).

It was Palincsar who introduced this technique for the first time and presented a very good model of reading comprehension in the form of predicting, questioning, summarizing and clarifying strategies, happened to be useful in class practicing. Rationally speaking, being a researcher such topic was selected in order to bring about some innovative changes among students, in reading plan as critical thinking, clear vision and high proficiency of speaking power and verbal communication could be developed. The researcher sought to facilitate and motivate students towards reading phenomenon in

self-directed learning, as it may provide a clear contour to distinct it from conventional method of reading. It was much difficult task to motivate them towards such a new way of learning. Even then the students enjoyed participating in these classes.

The researcher (as participant observer) made it possible to inculcate all this procedure alone being sure of the stumbling block. For this purpose, a pilot study was also conducted in order to prepare the test accurate and gathered information prior to larger study, according to the said model. Two kinds of model were applied to check the hypothesis RRS i.e. Reciprocal reading strategy and CRM i.e. conventional reading method.

Hypothesis of the study

To achieve the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were formulated:

The null hypothesis, there is no difference between Conventional Reading method and Reciprocal Reading strategy. ($H_0 = CRM = RRS$) Otherwise alternative hypothesis; there is difference between Conventional reading method and Reciprocal Reading strategy, would be accepted.

Review of Related Literature

For extensive reading function the researcher reviewed various literature, books, cited material as well as research journals. In Pakistan, majority students face problems in comprehensive study of the reading text, which is a big dilemma in Education region. In private sector the vacuum is filled via approaching the hitch from the very basis. On the other hand public sector students always remain low in capacity to produce such talent.

This study has been highlighted globally, on large scale perspective. Pondering over the current situation; researcher studied various articles, magazines and research theses in order to pursue the impact and significance of the present work.

Sullivan and Anne (1984) directed a two instructional studies Model. In this study they reported about Comprehension-fostering and Comprehension-Monitoring activities of seventh grade poor readers. They followed the reciprocal teaching method containing four strategies i.e. Predicting, Questioning, summarizing and clarifying. At the end of the study there was no improvement on the vocabulary measure, however on the comprehension measure, four of the six students made substantial gain on Reciprocal teaching. Finally, their studies remained successful and effective due to clear improvement in students' dialogue, quantitative improvement on comprehension tests and reliable transfer in assessment tasks and training.

Westernda Moore (1995) presented a paper on an experimental evaluation of trial implementation of Reciprocal Teaching strategy. Forty six students participated after standardized test with lowest score in seven and eighth grade classes. Among them 20 students were exposed for almost 16 sessions of Reciprocal Teaching, while 15 students were trained for 8 sessions with this method. Remaining 11 students were given no treatment in comparison to the Group of teaching. After 7 months when these students were assessed it was found that the students' comprehension level grows more than before.

Helen (1999) presented a case study on the Reciprocal Teaching approach for developing reading Comprehension ability. The purpose of the study was to help weaker advance readers. According to researcher, this strategy has been proved to be effective. It was found from the data that it could evolve readers' awareness in solving difficulties while reading. It was also identified after case study that it is highly important to receive training in Reciprocal Teaching approach as it's the essential part for learning and developing high skills for critical thinking in reading. It was concluded with the findings that there is difference between good reader and poor reader approach towards taking meaning and concept of the text. A good reader jumps over line while taking main idea abruptly. On the hand a poor reader reads word to word text and absorbs fully in to it, rather taking contextual meaning.

Hashey and Connors (2003) did action research on Reciprocal Teaching. Sampling of their study was 8 teachers from Grade 3-8. After reading Research work of Reciprocal Teaching they did action research in order to see whether this strategy works out or not. It was found that Reciprocal Strategy is very effective in 3-8 grades classes for improving Reading comprehension in fiction and non-fiction. Teachers were also guided for this new methodology.

Sarasti (2007) investigated the Effects of Reciprocal Teaching Comprehension Monitoring with a group of fifteen 3rd grade students reading at grade level. This study investigates the Curriculum base measurement to assess the reading comprehension growth of students. After measuring CBM maze Probe it was suggested that Reciprocal Teaching is effective in enhancing the reading comprehension aptitude of individual.

Agudelo (2010) conducted a study which was based on Research Project to analyze the viability of the Reciprocal Teaching implementation with sheltered instructions in EFL seventh grade students of secondary school to measure its learning process of English language. After implication of the study it was found that students were improved in reading comprehension by using such methodology. The findings of the study showed that this method

had positive effect on the participants' proficiencies. The nature of this study was qualitative. Most of the participants had a very low English proficiency level.

Anjum and Inamullah (2011) conducted a small scale study on Reciprocal Reading Strategy Model. The objectives of their study were to bring about innovative changes in Reading Comprehension via Reciprocal model. The mark population was 200 while 90 were selected via random sampling technique. In experimental group 58% students showed better result while control group remained low with 42%.

Reza et al (2013) conducted study on the importance of Reading in order to improve writing skill. True experimental design was formed by taking class of 104 through random sampling technique. The pre-test reliability rate was 0.95 while the post-test reliability test remained 0.97. The findings of this study depicted that students will motivate more towards reading if they realize the magnitude of reading.

The University of Washington also recommended this technique as to be useful and efficient as it could be for improving reading comprehension. It was found that adequate effort was paid in researches for reading enhancement in United States after 2002 "Act No Child Left Behind". They were also of the opinion that environment is not attuned in schooling period. The students cannot develop their idea and prototype in order to understand the content. (<http://depts.washingon.edu/centerme/recipro/h>) It's admitted that in our country (Pakistan) such proficiency has not been developed among students on primary as well as secondary level, especially in that area where the study held on the students' readiness for reading was found worst. (Pakistan KPK, Mardan).

Methodology

Nature of the Study

The study was experimental research in nature; pretest-posttest equivalent- groups design was used.

Population of the Study

The Target population was District Mardan female higher secondary schools KP, Pakistan. From the intermediate section, first year girls were part of the population.

Sample of the Study

The sample of the study encompassed four female higher secondary schools in urban and rural areas of District Mardan; namely School A (GGHSS Toru), School- B (GGHSS Shahdand), School- C (GGHSS Shehbaz Ghari), School- D (GGHSS Rustam Khel) , where 200 students were the focal point as sample from four higher secondary schools of District Mardan through stratified sampling technique, using formula of Krejcie and Morgan (Gay, 1990; Farooq, 2001). 50 female students were selected from each school. These students were further divided in to two groups G1 (experimental) and G2 (conventional) persisting 25 each. Pretest-Posttest equivalent design was patterned for both groups G1 and G2.

Research Design

The Researcher used the modified form of Gay (2000), Best (1986) and Farooq (2001) for the design of the Experimental Research using both qualitative and quantitative form of data collection. (Gay, 2000, p. 365) (Best,

1986, p.127) and (Farooq, 2001, p. 90). It is the only kind of research that can truly test hypothesis concerning cause and effect relationship (Gay, 2000, p. 342).

Instrumentation

The researcher (as participant observer) formed an observation sheet encompassed the following four steps of the reading activity in the observational sheet:

1. Predicting 2.Questioning 3.Summarizing 4.Clarifying with a modifying form of Palincsar. To trace qualitative data during reading session individually, systematic observation was opted to fulfill the requirement of the task. Experimental study was conducted, containing methodology both qualitative and quantitative data collection in order to check upon students' reading ability and making comparison of the reading techniques between two groups i.e. Group 1 and 2 (Experimental and control). The pretests posttest Equivalent Groups design was patterned for reading comprehension and for the validation of treatment of the Experimental Group (Best, 1986, p127; Gay, 2000; Farooq, 2001, p 90). Experimental process is the most precisely refined research technique (Mouly, 1963, p. 325). Check list (Blair et al, 1962) device was used in order to keep observation of the students during the study (Pearson & Doyle, 1987), (Pressely et al., 1987). The researcher put side by side two groups using Independent sample t-test analysis of pretest-posttest while using chi square as statistical tool for observational study.

Analysis of Data

Data was analyzed in systematic way. In order to get the data pretest-posttest equivalent designed and checklist were used. The data which was assembled through observation analyzed through percentage and chi square test, while pretest-posttest scoring results were manipulated via Independent sample t-test using SPSS.

Pretest and posttest were made according to the advice and instruction of Dr. Arshad Ali (Professor and Director IER) and Dr. Mujeburahman of language and linguistic department of English University of Peshawar. Check list observational sheet was constructed (Blair et al., 1962) in order to collect observations. The data of pretest-posttest and observation were collected and assembled in SPSS, MS Excel and MS Word.

The Research Procedure

Students were tested in pre-test post- test equivalent group design through which quantitative and qualitative data were received (Best, 1986). The time intervals between both tests were of eleven days. During their treatment information received via observational process with the help of check list device pertaining to rating scale concerned qualitative description (Blair et al., 1962). The marking of the students' tests was analyzed through Independent sample t-Test while chi-square test was used for observational data. All the results were illustrated in tabulation form.

Selected chapter (His first Flight) from English Text book for intermediate part I was schemed according to the time duration of the experiment. It had taken about 48 days in covering this trial in selected population areas (Urban rural areas of higher secondary schools Mardan) using stratified random sampling technique, students were divided in to two groups in selected sampling of higher secondary schools.

The experiment work took about 48 days.

Higher Secondary Schools and Class Room Setting material: English Text Book Chapter “His First Flight”

in reading performance. The calculated t-value 1.478 is not significant at 0.05 while p-value .141 is greater than 0.05. Therefore it's concluded that both G1 and G2 are equal in reading proficiency before treatment of RRS. The null hypothesis “there is no difference between CRM and RRS” is accepted here.

Independent Sample t-test

Post Test for Equality of Means of English subject

Mean difference	T	Df	p-value
9.29000	11.498	198	.000

After Levene’s test for equality variance the following interpretation are concluded:

The above table illustrated the mean difference of post test score remains about 9.29000 whereas t –test value is 11.498 at significant 0.05 while p-value .000 is less than 0.05 therefore null hypotheses is rejected and Research hypothesis is accepted

The Mean Difference

Scores out of 42	Number of observations	Mean	Std. Deviation
Post G-1	100	21.2500	6.65662
G-2	100	11.9600	4.57909

This table depicts the differences of mean corresponding to both posttest score of G1 and G2. The mean of G1 against 100 observations is 21.2500 while G2 against same observations is 11.9600. Standard Deviation corresponded to G1 scores remains 6.65662 while G2 4.57909. Assuming overall result of independent sample t-test of the posttest data it's illustrated that there is significant difference between RRS and CRM. Null hypothesis is rejected

Discussion

This new era is the period of science and technology where innovative system of education is being followed around the world. Since English language is globally standardized and considered as received language; therefore it is followed throughout the world to communicate and run the social and education system of life. In Pakistan every government put much effort for the sake of providing quality of education especially in English subject. It tries to drag and pull their dawdling and slow system forward as not to let it lagging behind. After having superficial

observation around the education system, the exercise of weak methodologies comes in focus to be changed by innovative system of learning. Students always face problem in the said subject from lower to higher classes. Whenever students promote to intermediate classes they undergo introversion in reading a single line loudly.

The researcher followed such strategy that was formerly introduced by Palincsar and Brown. (Palincsar & Brown, 1984, p. 117-175).

In Palincsar and Brown work, the students inculcate problems initially, where they were not able play the role of leader reader. They could not demonstrate phrases in dialogue but slowly and gradually they were able to complete the task of four steps strategy. The researcher also faced same tough situation being unaccompanied during the treatment. Initially they could not follow the four steps properly. After providing proper attention on the part of researcher they had been capable of performing the task. After treatment and observation it was illustrated by posttest that experimental group had been improved and enhanced their reading skills. They enjoyed the session with great zeal and curiosity.

In previous works; Anthony (1969), Watanabe (1984), Sullivan and Anne (1984) also conducted their respective studies on reciprocal reading strategies. Their objectives were successfully achieved parallel to the present study done by researcher.

The researcher selected pretest-posttest and checklist tools for acquiring data through them. Watanabe's study (1984) may be also compared with the present study of the researcher. He chose pretest-posttest equivalent design while using ANCOVA for data analysis. On the other hand researcher used chi square and independent sampling t-test for analysis of data. The p-value of the researcher study was .000 less than 0.05 therefore null hypotheses are rejected.

Contrary to the researcher study; Sullivan and Anne (1984) could not achieve all the objectives. Though the comprehension measure increased to substantial level but the vocabulary measure was not improved after analysis.

The researcher found magnificent changes in the reading proficiency of the students G1 after treatment of RRS. Likewise, Westera and Moore (1995) conducted experimental program where 46 students were treated for 16 sessions. And after 7 months when the group had been assessed there was found a magnificent change in the students' comprehension level. It grew more than before.

It is illustrated from the researcher's discussion that English teaching staff needs to be trained for imparting new strategies among students. As compare to the researcher's work same thing was identified after the case study of Helen (1999). It is highly important to receive training in Reciprocal teaching approach. Parallel to the researcher's findings it is concluded from the Helen's work that there is difference between good and poor reader after taking reciprocal teaching training.

During the experimental session it was observed from the students' motivation and interest that their understanding and critical thinking approach had been developed day by day. Such transformation was a tough and hard hitting task as there were no such English teachers to take the experimental classes in all 4 higher secondary schools. Keeping on efforts and utmost struggle on researcher's part made this study possible. Unlike previous researchers; Palincsar and Brown (1984) Hatcher and Tenent (2002), Hashey and Cannors (2003), the present researcher being participant observer controlled all 8 sessions alone. In order to provide the information about RRS to experimental groups was a big achievement of this work.

The time was divided according to the schedule prepared for both G1 and G2. Time distribution for Experimental group was more applicable as compared to control group. In 40 minutes classes students were given more chance to learn something in self-directed way. While in conventional classes plenty of time was consumed by teachers where students had less time to present themselves.

Conclusion

The underlying object of the study was to examine the effectiveness of "the Reciprocal Reading Strategy in reading comprehension in self-directed learning". In order to test its efficacy the strategy was compare with conventional way of reading methodology. The experimental study took 48 working days in order to complete this investigational toil. Pretest and posttest were administered with the interval of 11 days.

From the result of pretest, it was concluded that both G1 and G2 are in same position in reading comprehension. The result shows unsatisfactory starting in pretest. The calculated T-value 1.478 is not significant at 0.05 while p-value .141 is greater than 0.05. Eventually the null hypothesis "no difference between RRS (Reciprocal Reading Strategy) and CRM (Conventional Reading Method)" are accepted according to pretest. After taking experimental classes, it is concluded with the set of observational data, promising changes occurred among students behavior towards reading comprehension. At first they do not seem to take interest in reading classes. After interval of treatment the students of G1 gave the impression of zeal and wholeheartedness in classroom instructions.

Individually every school gave different result in posttest data. Whereas collectively it is concluded that the strategy proofed to be successful as compare to CRM.

On the basis of data analysis and students' comments it is concluded that 90% of the sample appreciated RRS as compared to CRM. The mean of G1 against 100 observations is 21.2500 while G2 against same observations is 11.9600, while p-value .000 is less than the significant level 0.05; therefore, it is concluded on the basis of test result that null hypothesis (there is no difference between CRM and RRS) is rejected while Research hypothesis is accepted.

To sum up; the result consummate from the conclusion , if the English teachers put into practice such technique in class room environment, it will strengthen a potential role in creating critical thinking skills and developing reading habit of the individual.

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